

EXPERIMENTAL RESEARCH ON DYNAMIC SHEAR PROPERTIES OF C/C COMPOSITE PINS

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ABSTRACT

A shear fixture was designed according to the needs of composite pins tests. To understand the strain rate sensitivity of carbon/carbon (C/C) composite pins, quasi-static and dynamic shear experiments were conducted by the means of electric universal test machine and drop weight impact testing system. The failure mechanism was verified by SEM (Scanning Electron Microscope) analysis. The results show that the shear strength of C/C composite pins is sensitive to strain rate, and the strain rate increased with increasing shear failure strength. Under quasi-static loading, the failure process shows “pseudo-plastic” characteristics, accompanied with large scale interface debonding. While under dynamic loading, it shows brittle fracture features without extensive debonding within bundles.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon/Carbon (C/C) composites have been widely used in aeronautical and aerospace fields due to their unique properties such as low density, high strength, high stiffness, and excellent high temperature mechanical properties. Researches shown that C/C composites with oxidation protective coating can survive at 2600°C^[1]. It is the attractive thermal structure material for shuttle nose, rocket motor nozzle, throat and chamber^[2]. Due to the restriction of fabrication technology, it is difficult to manufacture large-volume and complex-shape C/C composite structure directly^[3]. Alternatively, one promising way to achieving this complex structure by joining the simple components. C/C composites is the ideal joint material and has been used to connect the components of hypersonic flight vehicles, which serving in high temperature environment^[4]. Moreover, the reliability of the connections are severely challenged, due to the complex service environment with shock, vibration and noise. It is with great significance to study the failure mechanism of the C/C composite joints under dynamic environment.

Extensive works have been done on the quasi-static properties of C/C composites, such as tensile, compressive, flexural and shear^[5-13]. And the quasi-static properties of C/C composite joints have been also studied. Wang et al.^[4] studied the quasi-static mechanical properties of C/C composite bolts machined along different fiber reinforced directions. Min et al.^[14] examined the mechanical behaviors of C/C composite bolts with tightening torque. Much efforts has been spend on the dynamic mechanical properties of carbon fiber reinforced composites^[15-17], and its strain rate sensitivity was affirmed. However, little works have been focus upon the dynamic mechanical properties and the understanding of dynamic failure mechanism of C/C composite. Yuan et al.^[18-19] investigated the

dynamic compressive fracture behavior of C/C composites by using a modified split Hopkinson pressure bar. Their results shown that the compressive strength and stiffness increased at high strain rate. Moreover, it is the matrix and interface strength, which lead to the strain rate sensitivity of C/C composites. Li et al. ^[20] examined the strain rate effect on the longitudinal and transverse compressive behavior of C/C composites, and the strain rates of 700/s, 1400/s and 1800/s were applied by SHPB. They found that both the longitudinal and transverse compression behaviors of C/C composites were sensitive to strain rate, the dynamic properties increased significantly with increasing the strain rate.

In this paper, a shear fixture was designed and fabricated according to the needs of composite pins tests. To study the dynamic shear properties of as-received C/C composite pins, tests were conducted by electric universal test machine and drop weight impact testing system. Then, the shear fracture surfaces were observed by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) to understand the failure mechanisms of the composites.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Testing materials and apparatus

The C/C composite pins tested in this study were fabricated by Chemshine Carbon Co., Ltd., China. The preforms were made of polyacrylonitrile (PAN) based carbon fiber (T300, Toray, Japan). Fig. 1 shows the manufacturing process for C/C composites. The preforms were produced by the stacking sequence of one layer of 0° unidirectional fiber carbon cloth, one layer of short-cut fiber web, one layer of 90° unidirectional fiber carbon cloth, one layer short-cut fiber web. This process was repeated till the preforms gained a certain thickness, and then they were needle-punched vertical to the carbon cloth. The C/C composites were densified by the CVD (chemical vapor deposition), followed by heat treatment at a temperature of 2400 °C for graphitization. The as-received C/C composites were machined into cylindrical specimens with the dimensions of $\Phi 8.95\text{mm} \times 68\text{mm}$, along the 0° fiber direction. The average density of C/C composite pins was 1.62 g/cm³, which was calculated by measuring the mass and volume. The shear loading direction was in the carbon cloth plane along the 90° fiber direction.

Fig.1 Manufacturing process for C/C composites

The shear fixture (Fig. 2(a)) was designed and fabricated according to ASTM (American Society for Testing and Materials) B-769 associated with the needs of composite pins shear test. Fig. 2(b) shows the cross section of the fixture. The three inserted dies in the shear fixture were made of Cr12 tool steel with the Rockwell hardness from 60-62HRC, and the inner diameter is 9mm. To reduce the friction of center and outside dies, the mating surfaces had a finish of 0.4 μm . When conducting the experiment, the C/C composite pins were putting through the 3 inserted dies. Then, the mating surfaces were intimate contact by screwing the bolt. After that, the C/C composite pins were cut off by loading on the center die.

Fig.2 Shear fixture of C/C composite pins

2.2 Mechanical test

The quasi-static shear tests of C/C composite pins were conducted on an electric universal test machine (3367, Instron Co., Ltd.) at cross-head speeds of 5×10^{-6} m/s. The dynamic shear tests of C/C composite pins were conducted on a drop-weight impact machine (9250HV, Instron Co., Ltd.), Shown in Fig. 3. Dynamic shear tests were conducted with the loading speed of 1m/s, 5m/s and 10m/s, respectively. The number of effective specimens for each load case was 5. The shear strength of C/C composite pins can be calculated as follows:

$$\tau = \frac{P}{2S} = \frac{P}{2\pi\left(\frac{d}{2}\right)^2} = \frac{2P}{\pi d^2} \quad (1)$$

Where P is the shear load; S is the cross-section area of C/C composite pins; d is the average diameter of pins, which was determined by 6 times diameter measurement on the pins' shear plane.

Fig.3 Drop weight impact testing system

In the quasi-static test, the shear load (P) equals to the test load (P_t) recorded by test machine. In the dynamic shear test, the velocity of center die wasn't constant. So the acceleration of the center die should be taken into account, and the shear load can be expressed as follows:

$$P = P_t - ma \quad (2)$$

Where m is the mass of center die, $m=0.179$ kg; a is the acceleration of center die, which can be determined by the velocity gradient of cross-head.

3 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Fracture morphology of C/C composite pins

Fig. 4 shows the fracture surfaces of C/C composite pins under quasi-static shearing load (5×10^{-6} m/s). Large amounts of long fiber bundles were pulled out with a rough fracture surface (Fig. 4a). And the pulled-out fiber bundles were shattered to single fibers (Fig. 4b). The fiber bundles extensive deboned with some clean-surface fibers left, indicating the poor interaction between fiber and matrix (Fig. 4c). Furthermore, many fragments of carbon-matrix were left in the fiber bundles pulled-out holes (Fig. 4d).

Fig. 4 The fracture morphology of C/C composite pins under quasi static shearing load

Fig. 5 shows the fracture surfaces of C/C composite pins under dynamic shearing load (10m/s). Comparing with the quasi-static loading condition, there are fewer and shorter pulled-out fiber bundles on the fracture surfaces (Fig. 5a). Lots of fibers were cut off in the shear plane, and the fracture surface shown a large area of shear flat (Fig. 5b). Even though, few fiber bundles were pulled-out, they were surrounded by carbon-matrix, indicating the strong interaction between fiber and matrix (Fig. 5c). Few carbon-matrix clastics were left in the fiber pulled-out holes (Fig. 5d). Under dynamic loading, the C/C composites maintained relatively high integrity and continuity, which lead to a high anti-destroy capability.

The shear failure mode of C/C composites is sensitive to strain rate. Under quasi-static shearing load, it damaged with fully collapsed carbon-matrix and large quantities of tensile fractured fibers. While under dynamic shearing load, it damaged with high integrity of fiber bundles and clear shear failure mode in the shear plane.

Fig. 5 The fracture morphology of C/C composite pins under dynamic shearing load

3.2 The shear property of C/C composite pins

In this work, five effective specimens were tested for each loading case. The mean load-displacement curves were introduced to characterize the typical loading curves for each loading case. Fig. 6 shows the typical load-displacement curves of the C/C composite pins at different loading rates. It is obvious that the shear failure process of C/C composite pins at quasi-static and 1m/s loading case is characterized by “pseudo-plasticity”. At the initiation of loading, there were few damages in the C/C composites, and the load-displacement curves were linear. As the load slowly increased, the defects in the C/C composites fully developed and connected together. The carbon-matrix was broken into clastics and lost the binding force of the fiber bundles, so the fiber bundles lost the integral load-bearing capacity. At last, the C/C composites damaged with fibers tensile fractured successively, owing to discreteness of the fibers’ strength and stress. So the load-displacement curves of C/C composites reached the nonlinear part and a “load platform” followed. All these features can be indicated by the failure morphology of C/C composite pins shown in Fig. 4. While loading at the velocity of 5m/s and 10m/s, the loading time was very short and the defects in the C/C composites hadn’t enough time to develop. So fiber bundles’ integrity was maintained to some degree, and the composites had better mechanic properties. As the load increased, the fiber bundles reached its ultimate strength and occurred sudden breaking. So the load-displacement curves shows brittle failure without any “load platform”. All these features can be indicated by the failure morphology of C/C composite pins are shown in Fig. 5.

Fig.6 Typical loading curves of C/C composite pins

The results of shear behaviors of C/C composite pins are presented in Table 1. It is obvious that the shear strength of C/C composite pins is sensitive to loading rate. The ultimate load and the shear strength increased with the increasing of loading rate. Compared to the quasi-static, the ultimate load increased slightly for the loading case of 1m/s, then increased remarkably for the loading case of 5m/s and 10m/s, which increased from 4.89kN to 13.89kN and 18kN. The average shear strengths for the quasi-static loading (5×10^{-6} m/s) and dynamic loading (10m/s) are 40.12MPa and 150.03MPa, respectively, which increased by 274%.

Loading rate (m/s)	Average ultimate load (kN)	Average shear strength (MPa)	Standard deviation
5×10^{-6}	4.89	40.12	4.10
1	6.21	51.67	2.51
5	13.89	113.65	7.21
10	18.24	150.03	4.20

Table 1. Results of shear strength of C/C composite pins

3 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, the quasi-static and dynamic shear properties of C/C composite pins are studied, using a new designed shear fixture. And the macro- and micro-fracture morphology examinations were conducted to investigate the failure mechanism of C/C composite pins at quasi-static and dynamic loading cases. The results show that the failure mechanism of C/C composites varies with strain rate. The quasi-static shear failure behaves as fully collapse of matrix and successively tensile fractured of fibers, and the failure process shows “pseudo-plastic” characteristics. While the dynamic shear failure behaves high integrity of fiber bundle and clear shear failure mode in the shear plane, failure process shows “brittle fracture” characteristics. The shear strength of C/C composite pins is sensitive to strain rate, which increased with the increasing loading rate. Compared with the quasi-static shear strength (5×10^{-6} m/s), the dynamic shear strength (10m/s) is higher by 274%.

REFERENCES

- [1] Corral E L, Loehman R E. Ultra - High - Temperature Ceramic Coatings for Oxidation Protection of Carbon–Carbon Composites[J]. Journal of the American Ceramic Society, 2008, 91(5): 1495-1502.
- [2] Huang Qizhong. Fabrication, structure and application of high-performance carbon/carbon composites[M]. Changsha: Central South University, 2010.
- [3] Lan F T, Li K Z, Li H J, et al. Joining of carbon/carbon composites for nuclear applications[J]. Journal of materials science, 2009, 44(14): 3747.

- [4] Wang Jie, Li Kezhi, Guo Lingjun, et al. Microstructure and mechanical properties of C/C composite bolts[J]. *Journal Solid Rocket Technology*, 2012, 35(2): 248-252.
- [5] Song Q, Li K, Li H, et al. Increasing the tensile property of unidirectional carbon/carbon composites by grafting carbon nanotubes onto carbon fibers by electrophoretic deposition[J]. *Journal of Materials Science & Technology*, 2013, 29(8): 711-714.
- [6] Rao M V, Mahajan P, Mittal R K. Effect of architecture on mechanical properties of carbon/carbon composites[J]. *Composite Structures*, 2008, 83(2): 131-142.
- [7] Zhang J, Luo R, Xiang Q, et al. Compressive fracture behavior of 3D needle-punched carbon/carbon composites[J]. *Materials Science and Engineering: A*, 2011, 528(15): 5002-5006.
- [8] Li D, Yao Q, Jiang N, et al. Bend properties and failure mechanism of a carbon/carbon composite with a 3D needle-punched preform at room and high temperatures[J]. *New Carbon Materials*, 2016, 31(4): 437-444.
- [9] Feng L, Li K, Sun J, et al. Influence of carbon nanotube extending length on pyrocarbon microstructure and mechanical behavior of carbon/carbon composites[J]. *Applied Surface Science*, 2015, 355: 1020-1027.
- [10] Bradley L R, Bowen C R, McEnaney B, et al. Shear properties of a carbon/carbon composite with non-woven felt and continuous fibre reinforcement layers[J]. *Carbon*, 2007, 45(11): 2178-2187.
- [11] Yin Li, Zhao Donglin, Liu Hui, et al. Effects of graphitization on mechanical properties of 3D needled C/C composites[J]. *Transactions of Materials and Heatment*, 2011, 32(2): 10-15.
- [12] Wu X, Luo R. Mechanical properties investigation of carbon/carbon composites fabricated by a fast densification process[J]. *Materials & Design*, 2011, 32(4): 2361-2364.
- [13] Hu Y, Luo R, Zhang Y, et al. Effect of preform density on densification rate and mechanical properties of carbon/carbon composites[J]. *Materials Science and Engineering: A*, 2010, 527(3): 797-801.
- [14] Min Changwan, Tan Zhiyong, Long Liping. The mechanical behavior research of C/C composite bolt with tightening torque[J]. *Structure & Environment Engineering*, 2012, 39(3): 1-6.
- [15] Xuan C, Yulong L. Dynamic tensile behavior of two-dimensional carbon fiber reinforced silicon carbide matrix composites[J]. *Materials Science and Engineering: A*, 2011, 528(22): 6998-7004.
- [16] Li T, Fan D, Lu L, et al. Dynamic fracture of C/SiC composites under high strain-rate loading: microstructures and mechanisms[J]. *Carbon*, 2015, 91: 468-478.
- [17] Wang Zhenghao, Zhao Guiping, Ma Junfeng, et al. Experiment study on the strain rate behavior of carbon/epoxy composite materials [J]: *Acta Materiae Compositae Sinica*, 2007, 24(2): 113-119 .
- [18] Yuan Qinlu, Li Yulong, Li Hejun, et al. Quasi-static and dynamic compressive fracture behavior of carbon/carbon composites[J]. *Carbon*, 46(2008): 699-703.
- [19] Yuan Qinlu, Li Yulong, Li Hejun, et al. Strain Rate Sensitivity of C/C Composites under Compression[J]. *Journal of Inorganic Materials*, 2007, 22(2): 311-314.
- [20] Li D S, Duan H W, Wang W, et al. Strain rate and temperature effect on mechanical properties and failure of 3D needle-punched Carbon/Carbon composites under dynamic loading[J]. *Composite Structures*, 2017, 172:229-241.